

Title:

Application of Mathematical Modelling to Virtual Manufacturing

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Abstract: To analyze and modify manufacturing process in virtual environments, mathematical modelling can be used. Effects and behavior of the system are simulated by mathematical concepts in order to be analyzed and modified. So, different parameters of the process can be analyzed in order to be optimized. Thus, efficiency of part production can be increased by applying optimization methods to the simulated manufacturing process in virtual environments. Modification can also be presented to the simulated system in virtual environments by analyzing and decreasing errors of manufacturing process. Therefore, accuracy of produced parts can be increased in order to improve efficiency of part production. Overall, mathematical modelling can develop manufacturing process by providing analysis abilities in virtual environments.

Keywords: Mathematical modelling, Virtual manufacturing, Production optimization, Efficiency of part production, Accuracy of produced parts

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